

An Exploration of Patriarchal Dominance Through Discourse in Nathaniel Hawthorne's *The Scarlet Letter*

Dr. Abdus Samad¹, Tamkeen Inam², Arif Ullah Khan³

Abstract

This study aims at investigating patriarchal elements in *The Scarlet Letter* by applying the tool of Fairclough's 3D model. Research is qualitative in nature. This study has tried to investigate the logical association between language and society. It seeks to find out different effects of language through which one can learn about language and power relation. Likewise, the study argues that there is a close relationship between discourse, ideology and portrayal of characters in the social context. Through Critical Discourse Analysis of the selected text, the power of language has been identified. Additionally, the hidden agenda which is vivid in this discourse is also implicit. It has been found in the study that society devalues women and demeans their existence. Similarly, the patriarchy demolishes women's ability for creation, uniqueness and self-independency. Moreover, author of the selected text *Scarlet Letter* has revealed the atrocities of patriarchy and masculine hegemony through the medium of language. For instance, Hester Prynne accepts the shame of adultery but Dimmesdale (her male counterpart) stands silent and successfully hides himself before society. Critical Discourse Analysis is the broader field of study hence can be applied on variety of literary texts such as Henrik Ibsen's *Doll's House* and Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* for bridging two fields of literature and linguistics.

Keywords: Patriarchy, Masculine Hegemony, Discourse, Language, Power, Hester Prynne

1. Introduction

The most well-known and well-liked romance by Nathaniel Hawthorne, *The Scarlet Letter*, was first published in 1850 and is considered his "magnum opus". Research aims to study patriarchal values which have been depicted in the selected text by using Fairclough's 3D model as a theoretical framework. Additionally, the discourse of the novel regarding patriarchal values and its effects on the character of Hester Prynne has intrigued researcher for conducting the research. By applying Fairclough's 3D model of Critical Discourse Analysis on Nathaniel Hawthorne's novel *Scarlet Letter*, the power of language over society has been evaluated. The basic objective of this work is to expose the role of patriarchy in subjugating women through the medium of discourse. Moreover, it demonstrates the way power, dominance and ideology have been produced, maintained and are exploited through the agency of language. The story takes place in Puritan culture in the 17th century. Puritans society was patriarchal. Women were completely submissive to the demands of such society during this age. Females of that time were forbidden from expressing their wishes, thoughts, feelings, emotions and desires.

Yamin (2010) argues that women are undoubtedly dependents, first on their fathers and to their husbands. Likewise, in case of widowhood they are dependents of their sons, or any of her surviving male relatives. Moreover, puritans were of the view that women were only created for wicked temptations and as a result were more likely to fall in hell than men. Similarly, they believe that only men were capable of education, wisdom and freedom of expression. Moreover, Li (2006) described that the Patriarchal Puritan membership was based on the ability of that community to judge by external signs instead of the internal conscience of men. They didn't care about the sentiments of females as in the case of protagonist of the selected text.

Hester Prynne is the main character of the novel who is a young and beautiful lady. Unfortunately, she has brought a child into the world due to her illicit relation with an unknown person. She is condemned to wear a Scarlet Letter A on her breast and has to suffer public agony on the scaffold. Her character portrays the stereotyping of females and hegemony of males. But Hester rebels it by "an action marked with natural dignity and force of character" (Hawthorne, 1850, p45.) when she walked towards scaffold from the prison, she holds her head high and remains in public view without shedding a tear "as if by her own free will" (Hawthorne, 1850, p.50) Hester is the representative who suffers from irrational marriage with a physically and mentally deformed person named Chillingworth. Corresponding to his malformation with "one of the shoulder rose higher than the other" (Hawthorne, 1850, p.59), "Hester is tall with figure of perfect elegance on a large scale" (Hawthorne, 2001, p.54). Hence, she falls in a secret love affair with young and handsome priest named Dimmesdale and gives birth to an illicit child "Pearl".

1.1. Platform of Pillory

The scaffold is the last device Puritan authorities employ to constantly remind colonists of their tyrannical rule over them. The scaffold, which Hester uses to completely embody the gravity of her crime in front of the town, is situated in the 'Market Place'. The 'Market Place' serves as the hub of all activities in the community, which is why the

¹ Corresponding Author, Associate Professor/Chairman Department of English, Kohsar University Murree, Pakistan, abdussamad@kum.edu.pk

² MPhil Scholar, English Department, Qurtuba University of Science and Information Technology, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan

³ Assistant Professor of English, Government Post Graduate Jahanzeb College Saidu Sharif Swat, Pakistan

scaffold was placed here. The residents of the town were reminded of the effects of sin as they went about their everyday activities. The scaffold, according to the narrator, "was embodied and made manifest in this contrivance of wood and iron. The very idea of ignominy was embodied and made manifest in this contrivance of wood and iron" (Hawthorne 52). The scaffold was compared to the guillotine during the French Revolution because of how much terror the religious and political leaders had instilled in it.

1.2. Hawthorne's Perception of Masculinity

Greven asserts regarding Hawthorne's overall perspective on masculinity that "Hawthorne's male characters retreat when they might be expected to drive ahead, hide when others unceasingly seek" (56). The narrator represents the characters of Dimmesdale and Chillingworth to "target normative masculine behavior-effeminacy and teems with these emotionally, physically, and sexually inviolate male figures who reject both female and male companionship to get their revenge or hide their guilt" (Greven, 45).

In the *Scarlet Letter*, both of the main male characters such as Dimmesdale and Chillingworth must contend with an internal conflict between their emotions and reason, and both of them appear to fall short of Hester Prynne's moral strength. He suggests that unlike Dimmesdale, Hester never woefully loses her individual integrity, while her mind is not cramped by fears of the exposure of her sin, it being public, and that she is fortified by her moral independence and her love for him. Little Pearl, who represents the living proof of Dimmesdale's guilt, contributes to the torment of Dimmesdale by asking why "will he always keep his hand over his heart" (Hawthorne 296). Another dominant male figure that contrasts with Dimmesdale's fragility and gentility is Hester's husband, Roger Chillingworth. William Bysshe Stein in "Chillingworth as Faust and Mephistopheles" describes Chillingworth as the mixture of Faust and Mephistopheles and tries to explore Chillingworth's connection to the evil that goes beyond boundaries of earthly revenge.

1.3. Summary of *Scarlet Letter*

American author Nathaniel Hawthorne (1804-1864) specialized in both short stories and novels. The main themes of his work are typically connected to morality, history and religion. The collection of short stories being written by Nathaniel Hawthorne were collectively published in *Twice-Told Tales*. Moreover, Hawthorne's famous work is "Fanshawe" which was published for the first time. His work, *The Scarlet Letter* followed by a succession of other novels. Moreover, many works of Nathaniel Hawthorne feature moral metaphors including anti-puritan inspiration. Further, his fiction works also contained multitude of Hawthorne's writings centers within the setting of New England. Mostly, his fiction works have also been reviewed as the chunk of the humanistic discipline and more specifically black or deep romance.

The novel "Scarlet letter" by Nathaniel Hawthorne has been settled in the Puritan Massachusetts Bay Colony. The story of "Hester Prynne", protagonist of text, is actually the representative of 17th century. Hester is the central character of the novel. She is attractive young lady. Her husband, "Chillingworth" does not take care of his wife and hence shifted his wife to Boston while himself remains in Europe. Realistically, being a member of male chauvinist society Hester became a victim of her own emotions, love and care. She encountered a clergyman named "Dimmesdale", and hence gave birth to unlawful child, "Pearl". Now, the story then initiates with the scene a culprit has been punished for his act of adultery. Sadly, she becomes the victim of female stereotyping and hence received penalty for it and was forced to stand for three hours on the scaffold before the public. Moreover, she was compelled to embrace the shining Scarlet letter "A" on her trunk which proclaim Hester as an "Adulterous". Through the study of discourse or language, it has been portrayed that the major characters in the *Scarlet Letter* namely, Dimmesdale and Chillingworth including religious institutes display patriarchal power. Hester Prynne was rejected scorned and considered as a living allegory of sin after being charged with adultery. Additionally, female stereotyping has been demonstrated through contextual structures in the *Scarlet Letter* in a way when Hester was charged with penalty of embracing the fiery symbol "A" tattooed on her breast for her entire life. In fact, Hester shows full potential and strength in both her physical and mental attitude. She was caged by the harsh and rigid rules of patriarchal society. Unfortunately, the desires or wills of human heart can be easily sacrificed by restrictive rules of this society. Realistically, she lives alone in her community and becomes a living example of how through discourse, ideologies and identities can be constructed. Hence, Hester arrived at the journey of self-identification because she was independent. Moreover, she respects her own abilities to make decisions and listens to her conscience. She battles societal norms, customs and her own immorality. Her efforts turn the letter "A" from "Adulterous" to "Able". In this way Hester distinguished herself from traditional women, who are stereotyped as subservient to society's unjust patriarchal rules. Hence, Hester constructs her self-identity through her ideology and actions prevalent in novel's discourse.

1.4. Critical Discourse Analysis

The word “discourse” has been originally derived from Latin word *discursus* or conversations. For defining the term “Discourse” different linguists have been divided into two groups: One group considers discourse as only “Text” while other group considers it as “Speech”. Fairclough has divided discourse into two categories:

- Discourse is an abstract speech which considers language as a social activity hence draws more attention to substantial elements such as paragraphs, utterances, entire text or genres.
- Discourse is a practice that merely expresses the world. It also indicates how world helps in deconstructing and constructing the meaning of the text. Moreover, short conversations or sighs are also considered as discourse.

1.5. Fairclough’s 3D Model of CDA

Fairclough claims that CDA addresses societal issues, reconstructs identities and ideologies by revealing secret power abuses. Fairclough (1989), provides the theoretical study for recognizing ideological, social, religious and ethnic groups in any community that are abusing power and ideas. Additionally, Fairclough provided a more explanatory model for reviewing CDA. He distinguishes three variant stages of discourse: production and interpretation process and the written text (the product of first two levels). As a result, Fairclough’s model of CDA will be utilized as a study tool to discover the text’s concealed ideas in the selected text, “The Scarlet Letter”. Different linguists like Fowler (1997) and Van Dijk (1998) represent their thoughts regarding “Ideology”. According to Fowler (1997), Ideology is the collective way of people believe, expressions and their reactions in social spheres. Moreover, Van Dijk (1998) is of the idea that “Ideology” is actually the representative of practices habitual to society. But, Fairclough has designed a framework regarding the concept of ideology, Signification generated within power relations as a dimension of the exercise of power and struggle over power.

In fact, from other critical linguists, the approach of Fairclough’s regarding ideology is much different from other critical linguists. According to Fairclough, the power relations and superiority of class society develops through the ideologies that have been discriminated. Moreover, discourse which plays a key role in keeping relations of power is ideological in nature. Further, Fairclough expresses the confinement of different ideologies as an endowment to the power production.

Moreover, Fairclough (1992) defines that discourse is much dependent on ideology and hence served as container of ideas and beliefs or ideologies. Due to the fact that none of ideological competing discourses have an equivalent understanding in a specific society, the representative of these discourses actually impart them more power than other discourses. Moreover, Discourse considers the society’s interaction. As according to Fairclough the basic element of ideology cannot be evaluated in an undeviating way. In fact, the ideology regarding different spheres of life can be communicated through the utilization of discourse or language, considering as the most usual means of the conversation and discourse creation. Hence, discourse when gets the power of language, automatically becomes ideological. Hence, language is used for utilizing and composing influential and eloquent ideologies. Therefore, discourse used only for constructing, encouraging and controlling relations of dominance, suppression, and victimization.

In fact, this study investigates the discourse of the protagonist in the novel which helps in presenting ideology in a social mechanism. Nathaniel Hawthorne’s work under study has been evaluated on how patriarchal structure conventionalize females through discourse. Moreover, how Hester being member of patriarchal society-attainted self-identity. Hence, the objective of the study is actually the analysis of Fairclough’s systematic process of discourse analysis by practically implementing it on the discourse of major characters of *Scarlet Letter*. Hence, this evaluation is creative and innovative as the dialogues of the characters have been observed on the bases of discourse or language.

1.6. Problem Statement

The selected text, “*Scarlet Letter*” can be analyzed by applying Fairclough’s 3D model. Moreover, it has been observed that language and social structures presented in the text are inextricably linked. This study explores how do patriarchy maintains its hegemony through discourse.

1.7. Research Question

How major characters in the “*Scarlet Letter*” have displayed patriarchal power through the medium of language?

2. Literature Review

Review of the concerned literature available on the selected text *Scarlet Letter* and Fairclough’s 3D Model has been done in this chapter. Besides it, for initiating the study of Patriarchal structures, the articles which have been written by different scholars have also been reviewed.

2.1. Review of literature Related to Patriarchy in *Scarlet Letter*

Social patriarchy is a gender-based hegemonic value that is structured for the benefits of men but unfortunately disadvantages women. Alenezi (2012) in a work equalize colonialism with patriarchy in the novel. The anti-colonial reading of the novel is permitted through Hester’s struggle with what seem to be prevalent regulations regarding

gender, culture and religion. The only way for females to be liberated from this patriarchy is by rejecting it. Hawthorne, in this novel suggests that being a woman is in itself fighting back. Thus, it is only through womanhood that the female character can arrive at a reconciliation with themselves and with their consciences.

Furthermore, Jayasimha (2014) asserts significance of socio-psychological issues that surrounded, Hester Prynne, the central woman character of the novel. Hawthorne's concern is for the women who were the victim of the puritan Phallogocentrism and western moral systems construed and dominated by men.

Moreover, Hariyanti (2017) maintains that all the authorities were religious including her crime partner named as Dimmesdale. Moreover, this novel portrayed an image of Puritanical society of 17th century who is patriarchal hence implementing strict beliefs. Keeping in mind the harsh and stern religious beliefs, Hester is condemned and is forced to wear a badge of shame as her punishment till her death.

Chen (2017) in his study explores the double role played by Arthur Dimmesdale in the novel. Even being a wise and talented person, Dimmesdale accepts to be an irresponsible, coward and hypocrite. Arthur Dimmesdale's irresponsibility creates infinite hurdles and problems for Hester Prynne because he does not admit his involvement in sin of adultery for maintaining his reputation (as a Priest) among people. Moreover, Hawthorne criticizes the corrupt and devilish society as being dual standard in nature. Additionally, Hawthorne strongly attacks the evil nature of Puritanism which restrains people's minds, distorts their souls and demolish their lives. Likewise, Dimmesdale being a member of such distorting society hide his love for Hester Prynne and hence embraced death which ultimately becomes his fate.

Moreover, Hariyanti (2017) maintains that all the authorities were religious including her crime partner named as Dimmesdale. Moreover, this novel portrayed an image of Puritanical society of 17th century who is patriarchal hence implementing strict beliefs. Keeping in mind the harsh and stern religious beliefs, Hester is condemned and is forced to wear a badge of shame as her punishment till her death.

In addition to it, Zakaria and Rahman (2020) unfold Puritans hegemonic and inhuman attitudes in conducting state administration. The study reveals that the novel's protagonist becomes the victim of patriarchal beliefs. Instead, she becomes self-reliant and earns independence and identity as a result of her intellectual maturity, firm commitment and bold-decision.

Khan and Kazmi in a qualitative research 'Resolution, Autonomy and Accomplishment' (2021) argues that the heroine's journey passes through three phases from resolution to accomplishment. It has been analyzed that the power of determination can be used for changing human mindset. The study reveals that the novel's protagonist becomes self-reliant and earns independence and identity as a result of her intellectual maturity, firm commitment, and bold decision.

Likewise, Mie X (2019) avows Hawthorne's arrangement of settings senses and social background are usually highlighted. According to the spatial theories, especially Lefebure's Spatial Theory, the *Scarlet letter* was written. In this romance tale, Nathaniel Hawthorne created three spaces; physical, spiritual and social. These three types of spaces are not really juxtaposed; they are also intervening, inter-mingling, super imposing and sometimes contracting one another. The *Scarlet Letter's* tremendous vitality and enduring charm are due to Hawthorne's use of space to combine serious moral content with superb creative expressions. The novel's idea and meaning concerning the spiritual and ecological collapse of man-kind is also better stated through the construction of space. Hawthorne's pondering and transcendence of the real world is demonstrated in this work.

Likewise, Bayer (2020) evaluates Puritan's principles by analyzing heroine's creative ability and religious harsh rules as strategies of creative defiance. The *Scarlet Letter "A"* wore on her bosom becomes a transgressive method. The reflection of early nineteenth-century New England Transcendentalist speech indicates how Hester converts her symbol of shame into an expression of identity.

Bouzenag (2020) has portrayed a common subject of women being subjected to oppression by theocratic communities. However, the aforementioned facts analyze the connection between the traditional and religious confines and their contribution towards the oppression of women in two separate settings: the 17th century Puritan New England and the Taliban in Afghanistan in the 19th century. Moreover, the twin characters of these respective novels have been taken as case studies for this purpose.

Moreover, Arai (2022) focuses on Pearl and the novel's depiction of maternity. Pearl refuses to conform to Puritan norms throughout the novel and represents a new perspective on women's roles. As a "mother's child," Pearl has the potential to subvert Puritan society's patriarchal order, and the final reunion of Dimmesdale, Hester, and Pearl on the scaffold can be seen as a triumph of maternity.

3. Research Methodology

In order to explore the masculine hegemony in the selected text *Scarlet Letter*, both descriptive and analytical methods have been used. First, the researcher has deconstructed excerpts, paragraphs and sentences related to the concept of

how patriarchy objectifies woman through the medium of language. Secondly, the researcher analyzed three different levels of Fairclough's model of CDA the so called textual, descriptive and interpretation. Hence keeping in mind while assessing prior investigations connected to the novel's main objectives and question, the researcher has collected data and interpreted them accordingly.

4. Analysis and Discussion

4.1. Description of Patriarchal Power Through Language in The Scarlet Letter

The careful analysis of the selected text "Scarlet Letter" has been done with the tool of Fairclough's 3D model. The analysis is divided into three stages: Description, Explanation and Interpretation as per theoretical framework. Mostly, it chiefly focuses on the heroine of the novel, Hester Prynne. After facing trials and tribulations of patriarchal system she believes in her own instincts. Finally, through her own code of conduct and inner strength she gets her self-identity. The Scarlet Letter consists of 24 chapters each of them contains the themes of Patriarchy that researcher would try to search out in the selected text for analysis.

4.1.1. Excerpt 1

A multitude of bearded men, in gloomy-colored outfits and grey steeple, crowned hats, together with women, some wearing hoods, and others bear headed, was gathered in frontage of a wooden structure, the door of which was deeply wooded with oak studded with iron spikes (Hawthorne,1850, p.48).

4.1.1.1. Description

It has already been described that description likely to emphasizes the identification of the standard attributes and properties of the written text such as features or characteristics of discourse speech patterns, usage patterns and syntax production, etc. In fact, lines given in the excerpt have been taken from the text. Hawthorne has portrayed patriarchal society, he, clearly depicts the setting is in prison and the preparatory. It is clear that something bad has been done and hence someone is being punished for his or her sin. Now, the offender is the female protagonist of the novel, Hester Prynne. In the given extract, the sentence structure and selection of words such as "bearded men, iron spikes, bear headed" shows the gender discrimination or gender construction and the role of the medium of language and highlight gender inequality, discrimination and subjugation. Moreover, Puritans can be recognized by their dressing such as all were in 'black-attire'. Moreover, expressions such as 'iron-door spikes' and 'oak-timbered doors' unfold harsh nature of Puritans. Even the architecture of the building depicts the prevalence of this belief system, which was popular among the Puritans in 17th century.

4.1.1.2. Interpretation and Explanation

The stage of interpretation analyzes participants' procedures of text production as well as interpretation. Moreover at the stage of explanation the hidden ideologies are explored. The given excerpt depicts the somber and depressing mood that altogether with the title "Prison door" immediately grabs the reader's attention. The strict puritanical patriarchal beliefs of 17th century are strongly prevalent in the novel. Moreover, the most dramatic and significant scene in the novel is centered around "scaffold". Hence, the above passage portrays the "scaffold scene" where all the members of community gathered for the humiliation of "Hester Prynne" for her act of adultery. The phrase "iron spikes" signals power and authority over females. The 'bearded men' symbolizing tyrannical rule of patriarchal society for women. Furthermore, at the scaffold scene, someone called "Come along Madam Hester and show your scarlet letter in the market place (Hawthorne,1850, p. 55). In fact, the center of attention in this scaffold scene is the letter "A" which has been worn by Hester Prynne, fantastically embroidered and illuminated upon her bosom. The letter "A" stands for adultery as the source of punishment for her as announced by the religious scholars of the patriarchal society.

4.1.2. Excerpt 2

What can thy silence do for him, except it tempts him-yea, compel him, as it were to add hypocrisy to sin? The young pastor's voice was tremulously sweet, rich, deep and broken. That feeling that it so evidently manifested words, caused it to vibrate within all hearts, and brought the listeners into one accord of sympathy (Hawthorne,1850, p.69).

4.1.2.1. Description

In the above extract, the words have been spoken by Dimmesdale (the renowned priest) before the patriarchal society, when Hester was standing on the place the so called scaffold and is reviewing punishment of her bad or evil deed. The lexical choice in the passage is ironic in nature and showing male's hypocrisy. Moreover, the selection of words in the above extract and the close structure of the words portrays women inequality at the hands of strict patriarchal society. Additionally, words have association with different things and human beings, for example, association of pain, blood and medicine with a needle. The use of adjectives in the text such as, "sweet, rich, deep, and broken" signify their association with secret being kept hidden by Dimmesdale. In Patriarchal system, there is discrimination in every field of life. Language determines human's behavior in the society. Different choices of vocabulary involving

the description of variety of items and the words “silence and heart” are related to female’s class. Through in-depth study of the passage it has been analyzed that words such as softness and politeness are synonymous to women.

4.1.2.2. Interpretation and Explanation

The male characters Governors Richard Bellingham and John Winthrop and Ministers John Wilson and Arthur Dimmesdale work together, serving as the religious and political authorities of The Scarlet Letter’s fictional colony. These men as the colonist leaders fail to “understand the heights and depths of human nature” (Zuckert,164). In fact, the two principle sinners in the Scarlet Letter are Hester Prynne and the Reverend Mr. Arthur Dimmesdale. There is a wide difference between attitudes of these two individuals towards sin which they have committed. Their case of adultery is aggravated due to Dimmesdale’s hypocrisy and his style of wearing a mask of piety for several years before he makes up his mind for public confession. In the above passage, when Hester is standing on scaffold before religious ministers including Dimmesdale, she is compelled to unveil the name of her partner but she denies and stands still with sheer bravery and confidence before strict and iron-handed patriarchal society and shows how females become a victim of male dominated society.

4.1.3. Excerpt 3

There was the taint of deepest sin in the most sacred quality of human life, working such effect that the world was the only darker for this woman’s beauty and the more lost for the infant that she had borne (Hawthorne,1850, p. 50).

4.1.3.1. Description

The above extract unfolds the darker effects of sin on Hester’s beauty. In the above passage, the sentence structure and selection of words depicts the gender discrimination and role of language in women’s inequality and subjugation in terms that for her as well as for her ‘infant’ the world would be “darker”. In addition to it, the use of expression ‘sacred quality of human life’, expresses that how a single sin demoralizes person’s life. Moreover, in the extract, past tense is used. Additionally, the comparative degree of adjective such as the word ‘darker’ expresses the bleak effects of adultery. The use of superlative form of adjective ‘deepest’ expresses the severity of the situation. Furthermore, the use of apostrophe with the word ‘women’ suggests relational value with the adjacent word ‘lost’. Hence, indicating how patriarchal society devalues female’s beauty. Moreover, the use of demonstration pronoun “that” refers to her infant ‘Pearl’. The use of conjunction “and” works for bridging the sentence hence helps in making idea coherent. Moreover, the phrase “more lost for the infant that she had borne” portrays how an innocent infant becomes only ‘darker’ for Hester’s feminine beauty. The use of adjective ‘darker’ portrays how the world becomes horrible for the female and makes her survival impossible.

4.1.3.2. Interpretation and Explanation

Unfortunately, the horizontal and masculine structure of puritanical society celebrates men as the ruling energy of the world. on one hand, the male dominated society views women as mother hence sacred and on the other hand exploits her for its own self-centered end. In fact, the selected text reflects patriarchal values. It is obvious from the novel the political structure of the Massachusetts colony is patriarchal one. Those who assume authority rule the people as its in the text that these “fathers and founders of the common wealth, the statesman, the priest and the soldier are essentially male” (Hawthorne,1850, p 201). In fact, the female remains entirely un-represented and the powerful hold of patriarchy is maintained by the exclusively male government. In the above passage, there is the brief reflection of social structure of society of that time. Hester is much beautiful but the “deepest sin” of adultery which is being considered as the ‘sacred quality of human life’ makes her ‘beauty’ only ‘darker’ for the world. Moreover, Pearl (an infant) which Hester had born has been considered as “loss” of Hester’s identity before patriarchal values. In fact, Hester and Dimmesdale are drowning to each other by desires that cannot be controlled by the values of social, legal, and religious institutions. They give an insight to their natural impulse which leads to conception and reproduction. Hester’s pregnancy is considered by patriarchal society as the most heinous crime however it is the natural outcome of the basic human impulse. The relationship between Hester and Dimmesdale explores the tension between natural desires and the ways in which society tries to control human nature by imposing their self-made rules and laws. Hester Prynne’s frigidity and coldness makes it clear that an act of “adultery” left a significant impact on her personality regardless of how the town’s residents measure the severity of her sin. The letter ‘A’ has such a profound effect that it gives a shock to the offender’s entire soul.

5. Conclusion

Concluding, the research question which have been mentioned in the first chapter of thesis have been explored. Moreover, the analysis of each research question have been done according to the three levels of Fairclough’s Model of Critical Discourse Analysis. At the textual stage, description of the selected passage from the novel “Scarlet Letter” has been realized. Additionally, the production and consumption of the text has also been analyzed from the discourse of selected text. Moreover, the answer to each research question has been explored by keeping in view the research objectives. Firstly, owing to the first research questions regarding influence of patriarchy through the medium of the

language was explored. Through the close textual analysis of the passage it has been observed that different grammatical features, lexical contexts, relational and experiential expressions from the medium of discourse. The language used by major characters of the novel, mostly including, male sector, spread the harsh and rigid rules of patriarchy. Moreover, at the levels of interpretation and explanation it has been realized that Hester becomes the tool at the hands of male chauvinist society. In addition to it, Hester Prynne the protagonist of the selected text, "Scarlet Letter" basically becomes the victim of power dominated sector. Similarly, Hester Prynne is actually a representative of 17th century society of Massachusetts. It has been observed closely that Hester committed an act of adultery and gives an outlet to her natural sexual desire due to negligence of her husband Chillingworth. Sadly, Chillingworth, both physically and mentally does not match with Hester, who is perfect, beautiful, charming and young lady. It is also noticeable that Hester committed sin with the most prestigious personality of society, named "Dimmesdale". But, Dimmesdale maintains his reputation and he left Hester before public selfishly. Even he stands above the balcony, and looks at her and forced her to reveal the name of his fellow partner. Through the discourse implied by Hawthorne being spoken by Dimmesdale, it has been realized that patriarchal society is based on dual standards.

References

- Alenezi, M. (2022). Hester's resistance against the patriarchal society: A postcolonial reading of. *Ars Aeterna*, 14(1), 1-9.
- Arai, K. (2022). "I am mother's child": Nathaniel Hawthorne's Moderate Feminism in *The Scarlet Letter*.
- Bayer, T. (2020). Creative Agency in *The Scarlet Letter*. University of Edinburgh Postgraduate *Journal of Culture and the Arts*.
- Bouzenag, C. (2020). Female Agency vs. Passivity in Nathaniel Hawthorne's *The Scarlet Letter* and Khaled Hosseini's *A Thousand Splendid Suns*: A Comparative Study.
- Chen, Y. (2012). On Arthur Dimmesdale's Double Personalities as Revealed in Hawthorne's *The Scarlet Letter*. 9.
- Fairclough, N. (1992). Discourse and text: Linguistic and intertextual analysis within discourse analysis. *Discourse & society*, 3(2), 193-217.
- Fowler, R. (1997). *Critical discourse analysis: The critical study of language*.
- Greven, David. *The Fragility of Manhood: Hawthorne, Freud, and the Politics of Gender*. Columbus: Ohio State University Press, 2012. Print.
- Hawthorne, Nathaniel. *The Scarlet Letter*. London: Knight and Son, 1854. Print
- Hariyanti, T. & Nurhayati, D. (2017). Pearl in Hawthorne's *The Scarlet Letter*: a socio-religious perspective. *AWEJ for Translation & Literary Studies, Volume, 1*.
- Jayasimha, P. (2014). Between passion and sin: a postmodern Feminist approach to Nathaniel Hawthorne's *The Scarlet Letter*. *International Journal of English Literature and Culture*, 2(6), 68-72.
- Mei, X. (2019). Beyond Nature and Subjectivity-The Issues of Space in Nathaniel Hawthorne's *The Scarlet Letter*. *Int'l J. Soc. Sci. Stud.*, 7, 13.
- Van Dijk, T. A. (1998). Ideology: A multidisciplinary approach. *Ideology*, 1-384.
- Wang, Y. (2010). A Representative of the New Female Image--Analyzing Hester Prynne's Feminist Consciousness in *The Scarlet Letter*. *Journal of Language Teaching & Research*, 1(6).
- Yueling, L. (2006). Hester Prynne, a Heroine of Anti-Puritanism. *Journal of Yulin Teachers College*, 27, 32-36.
- Zakaria, Z., Duli, A., & Rahman, F. (2020). Puritan's Hegemony in the Nathaniel Hawthorne's *The Scarlet Letter*. *Language Circle: Journal of Language and Literature*, 15(1), 43-49.
- Zuckert, Catherine H. "The Political Thought of Nathaniel Hawthorne." *Polity* 13.2 (1980): 163- 83. Print.